

to yield **4** which were converted to their corresponding hydrazides (**5**) by refluxing with ethanolic hydrazine hydrate (Scheme 1). These compounds when reacted with phenyl isothiocyanate in ethanol gave the corresponding *N*¹-substituted-quinolin-2(1*H*)-one thiosemicarbazides (**6**). The cyclisation of **6** yielded *N*¹-substituted five-membered heterocyclic quinolin-2(2*H*)-ones (**7**, **8** and **9**).

Scheme 1

Synthesis of some New *N*¹-Substituted-quinolin-2(1*H*)-one Derivatives

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Manuscript received 8 August 1991, accepted 28 October 1991

QUINOLINE derivatives possess various biological activities¹. 2-Substituted-thioquinolinamide acts as a reagent for the determination of copper(II)². So far, some work has been done on the *N*¹-substituted quinoline derivatives. Since hydrazides, thiosemicarbazides, triazoles, oxadiazoles and thiadiazoles are associated with antibacterial activity, it was considered worthwhile to incorporate these structural moieties in the *N*¹-position of quinoline nucleus.

The key intermediates, *N*¹-hydrazidoquinolin-2(1*H*)-ones were prepared by the reaction of substituted-quinolin-2(1*H*)-one with ethyl chloroformate in presence of potassium carbonate in dry acetone

Experimental

Melting points were determined in open capillary tubes and are uncorrected. Ir spectra (KBr) were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer 23 spectrophotometer and pmr spectra (TFA) on a Perkin-Elmer R-32 spectrometer using TMS as internal standard. Purity of the compounds was checked by tlc.

Substituted acetoacetanilides were prepared by known method³.

4-Methyl-2-quinolones (3): A mixture of acetoacetanilide (**2a**; 0.1 mol) and concentrated H₂SO₄ (40 ml) was heated on a water-bath at 70–80° for 0.5 h and for 1.0 h at 100°, then cooled and poured in ice-cold water (500 ml) with constant stirring. The resulting solid was dried and recrystallised from ethanol: **3a** (81.76%), m.p. 227° (Found: C, 75.4; H, 5.6; N, 8.75. Requires: C, 75.47; H, 5.66; N, 8.81%); ν_{max} 3 200–3 100br (NH), 1 665 (amido

C=O) and $1\ 600\ \text{cm}^{-1}$ (C=C); δ 2.45 (3H, s, CH₃), 6.2 (1H, s, =CH), 7.8–7.0 (1H, dd, J_{ortho} 8.0 Hz, J_{meta} 2.5 Hz, C₆-H), 7.05–7.15 (1H, d, J_{ortho} 8.0 Hz, C₅-H), 7.15–7.35 (1H, dd, J_{ortho} 8.0 Hz, J_{meta} 2.5 Hz, C₈-H) and 8.4 (1H, s, br exchangeable with D₂O, CONH); 3b (80%), 258°; 3c (68%), 213°.

N¹-Carbethoxy-4-methyl-2-quinolin-2(1H)-ones (4): A mixture of 4-methyl-2-quinolin-2(1H)-one (3a; 0.03 mol) and ethyl chloroformate (0.03 mol) in dry acetone containing anhydrous potassium carbonate (2 g) was refluxed for 24 h, then cooled and the solvent was removed under reduced pressure. The resulting white solid was washed with water and recrystallised from ethanol: 4a (77.0%), m.p. 87° (Found: C, 68.6; H, 5.25; N, 5.75. Requires: C, 68.88; H, 5.39; N, 5.81%); ν_{max} 1 780 (ester C=O), 1 665 (amido C=O) and $1\ 600\ \text{cm}^{-1}$ (C=C); δ 1.3 (3H, t, J 8 Hz, ester CH₃), 2.45 (3H, s, =CH₃), 4.2 (2H, s, OCH₂), 6.2 (1H, s, =CH) and 7.0–7.8 (3H, m, ArH); 4b (75%), 48°; 4c (86%), 50°.

N¹-Hydrazido-4-methyl-quinolin-2(1H)-ones (5): To a solution of 4a (0.01 mol) in ethanol (40 ml), hydrazine hydrate (0.01 mole) was added and the reaction mixture was refluxed on a water-bath for for 2 h, then cooled and the resulting solid was recrystallised from ethanol: 5a (74%), m.p. 220° (Found: C, 60.7; H, 5.0; N, 19.20. C₁₁H₁₁O₂N₃ requires: C, 60.83; H, 5.07; N, 19.35%); ν_{max} 3 350 (NHNH₂) and $1\ 665\ \text{cm}^{-1}$ (amido C=O); δ 2.4 (3H, s, CH₃), 2.5 (2H, s, NH₂) and 7.0–7.5 (4H, m, ArH); 5b (73%), 265°; 5c (83%), 273°.

4-Aryl-1-(N¹-quinolinoyl)thiosemicarbazide (6): A mixture of 5a (0.001 mol) and phenyl isothiocyanate (0.001 mol) in ethanol (25 ml) was refluxed for 3–4 h, then cooled and the solvent was removed under reduced pressure. The resulting residue was triturated with water and the solid obtained was recrystallised from ethanol: 6a (76%), m.p. 84° (Found: C, 61.30; H, 4.50; N, 15.80. C₁₈H₁₆O₂N₄S requires: C, 61.36; H, 4.55; N, 15.91%); ν_{max} 3 350–3 400 (NH), 1 670br (CONH) and $1\ 325$ – $1\ 355\ \text{cm}^{-1}$ (C=S); δ 2.4 (3H, s, CH₃), 6.2 (1H, s, =CH), 7.5–7.6 (9H, m, ArH) and 7.8 (1H, s, NHCO exchangeable with D₂O); 6b (85%), 113°; 6c (80%), 60°.

5-Aryl-2-[N¹-(4'-methylquinolin-2'-one-1'-yl)]-5-mercapto-1,3,4-triazole (7a): Compound 6a (0.001 mol) was refluxed with 2N NaOH (2 ml) for 3 h, then cooled, filtered and the filtrate was acidified with glacial acetic acid. The resulting solid was recrystallised from ethanol: 7a (62%), m.p. 266° (Found: C, 63.3; H, 4.3; N, 17.30. C₈H₁₄ON₄S requires: C, 63.35; H, 4.35; N, 17.39%); ν_{max} 3 250–3 300 (NH), 1 664 (amido cyclic C=O) and $1\ 620\ \text{cm}^{-1}$ (C=N); δ 2.4 (3H, s, CH₃), 6.2 (1H, s, =CH), 7.0–7.9 (9H, m, ArH), 11.5–12.0 (1H, s, exchangeable with D₂O, 5H).

5-Arylamino-2-(4'-methyl-quinolin-2-one-1'-yl)-1,3,4-oxadiazole (8a): To 6a (0.001 mol) in NaOH (4N, 4 ml), I₂ in KI was added till colour of I₂ persisted and the mixture was further concentrated

for 4–5 h, then cooled and poured into ice-cold water. The resulting solid was recrystallised from ethanol, (77.5%), m.p. 283° (Found: C, 67.8; H, 4.3; N, 17.5. C₁₈H₁₄O₂N₄ requires: C, 67.92; H, 4.40; N, 17.6%); ν_{max} 3 150–3 250 (NH), 1 665–1 670 (NHCO) and $1\ 620\ \text{cm}^{-1}$ (C=N); δ 2.45 (3H, s, CH₃), 4.5 (1H, s, NH), 6.2 (1H, s, =CH) and 7.0–7.5 (9H, m, ArH).

5-Arylamino-2-(4'-methylquinolin-2'-one-1'-yl)-1,3,4-thiadiazole (9a): Compound 8a (0.001 mol) dissolved in phosphoric acid (5 ml) was heated at 120° for 50 min and kept overnight. It was then poured into ice-cold water and the resulting solid was recrystallised from ethanol, (76.5%), m.p. 298° (Found: C, 64.6; H, 4.10; N, 16.7. C₁₈H₁₄ON₄S requires: C, 64.67; H, 4.19; N, 16.77%); ν_{max} 3 200–3 300 (NH), 1 665 (amido C=O), 1 610–1 620 (C=N) and 700–720 cm^{-1} (C–S–C); δ 2.4 (3H, s, CH₃), 4.8 (1H, s, NH), 6.15 (1H, s, =CH) and 7.0–7.8 (9H, m, ArH).

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